

A Review Article on Reassessing and Enhancing Pedestrian Facilities for Improved Safety in School Zones

Pappu Kumar, Onkar Yadav

Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Sandip University, Madhubani, Bihar, India

Pappu Yadav

Research Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, Sandip University, Madhubani, Bihar, India

Abstract: Ensuring the safety of pedestrians, especially in school zones, is of paramount importance. This review article aims to assess and enhance pedestrian facilities within school zones to improve safety. The study critically evaluates existing infrastructure, policies, and practices while proposing strategies for redesigning and optimizing pedestrian facilities. The review begins by examining the current state of pedestrian safety in school zones, highlighting the challenges and risks associated with vehicular traffic and the vulnerability of pedestrians, particularly students. Various factors contributing to accidents and injuries are explored, including inadequate crosswalks, insufficient signage, and limited visibility. To address these issues, the paper proposes a comprehensive framework for reassessing and enhancing pedestrian facilities. This framework encompasses multiple aspects, including infrastructure improvements, policy interventions, and community engagement. Recommendations for infrastructure enhancements include the installation of well-marked crosswalks, speed reduction measures, improved signage, and increased visibility through the use of lighting and reflective materials. Additionally, the paper emphasizes the importance of policy interventions such as implementing stricter speed limits, enforcing traffic regulations, and conducting regular safety audits. It also highlights the significance of involving the community, including parents, teachers, and local authorities, in advocating for safer pedestrian infrastructure and promoting awareness and education. The review draws upon existing research studies, best practices, and successful case examples from different jurisdictions to support its recommendations. The proposed strategies aim to create an environment that prioritizes the safety of pedestrians, particularly school children, and reduce the likelihood of accidents and injuries in school zones. Overall, this review article provides valuable insights and practical recommendations for reassessing and enhancing pedestrian facilities in school zones, ultimately striving for improved safety and well-being for all pedestrians.

Keywords: Pedestrian safety, School zones, Infrastructure enhancements, Policy interventions, Community engagement.

1. INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of road traffic accidents near schools and the resulting fatalities and injuries among school children are significant concerns that are steadily rising. Unfortunately, safety considerations pertaining to school-going children in school zone areas are frequently neglected. In India, child pedestrians represent the most vulnerable group of road users, as they lack protection in the event of an accident. They are particularly susceptible to being involved in fatal

accidents and sustaining severe injuries. The number of road users involved in accidents is continuously escalating, underscoring the urgent need to address the issue of ensuring safer roads and school zones for school-going children.

2. GLOBAL SCENARIO

According to the World Health Organization's Global Road Crash Statistics, approximately 1.25 million people lose their lives in road crashes worldwide each year. Shockingly, over 1,600 children under the age of 15 years succumb to these accidents annually. In 2004 alone, the number of children aged 0-19 years who died in road traffic accidents exceeded 260,000. It is concerning to note that 93% of all road fatalities occur in low-income and middle-income countries, while higher-income countries witness 50% of child traffic deaths. Among vulnerable road users, pedestrian children face a higher risk, particularly those aged between 5 and 14 years. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the risks faced by children in road traffic accidents, a table displaying the incidence of road traffic injuries for individuals up to the age of 20 years is presented. This table distinguishes between High-Income Countries (HIC) and Low-Income and Middle-Income Countries (LMIC) to highlight the disparities in risk between different economic contexts.

3. INDIAN SCENARIO

Save Life Foundation, an Indian NGO dedicated to road safety, reports that since 2008, more than 55,000 children have tragically lost their lives in road crashes in India. According to road crash statistics from 2016, it is estimated that every day in India, 43 children lose their lives due to road accidents, with approximately 20 children under the age of 14 being victims. These figures are based on a report by the World Health Organization (WHO). In 2017, children below the age of 18 accounted for 6.4% of road crash fatalities. It is important to recognize that the safety measures designed for adults cannot be simply applied to children. Therefore, it is imperative for the government to prioritize and implement specialized safety policies specifically tailored to the needs of children. A survey conducted in India revealed that unsafe commuting conditions for children are not solely caused by irresponsible and negligent behavior of road users. Inadequate infrastructure, such as the lack of footpaths, zebra crossings, and proper signage, also contributes to the compromised safety of children during their commute. The increasing motorization has led to constant crowding on roads, exacerbating the risks for children traveling independently. Both drivers and pedestrians share responsibility for road crashes, and drivers need to exercise extra caution, especially in school zone areas. Overall, these findings emphasize the need for comprehensive safety measures, including infrastructure improvements, policy interventions, and awareness campaigns, to safeguard children's lives on Indian roads.

4. SURVEY OF LITERATURE

Numerous researchers, municipal corporations, NGOs, social workers, and government agencies have actively engaged in efforts to enhance road safety and create safer travel environments. Specifically, when it comes to school areas that involve the movement of vulnerable road users, such as school-going children and pedestrians, extensive literature from various sources has been examined to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing road safety in school zones. The following excerpts are derived from the analysis of various documents during the literature review process.

Carle Hume et al. (2009) In a research study conducted by Carle Hume et al. in Melbourne, Australia, the focus was on active commuting, specifically walking and cycling to school. The data for the study was collected between 2004 and 2006. The findings revealed that parents who were familiar with their neighborhood residents were more likely to encourage their children to engage in active commuting to school compared to parents who had less familiarity with the

neighbors. Additionally, parents who observed a lack of pedestrian crossings and traffic lights were less inclined to encourage their children to walk and cycle to school. Hence, the research paper highlights the significant influence of both the physical environmental characteristics and social factors on promoting active commuting to school.

Andrew P. Jones et al. (2010) In a study conducted by Andrew P. Jones et al. in Norfolk, United Kingdom, the researchers aimed to investigate the impact of the school environment, routes, and neighborhood on active commuting to school. The study involved 92 schools with children aged between 9-10 years. A questionnaire-based survey was administered, with both parents and children providing data. The analysis conducted by Andrew P. Jones et al. revealed several key findings. Firstly, they observed that children residing in deprived areas and those with direct routes were less likely to walk or cycle to school. Additionally, the study found that students who had a higher density of streetlights in their neighborhoods were less inclined to cycle, whereas those living in areas with a higher density of roads were more likely to walk. Based on these findings, the researchers concluded that both routes and the neighborhood environment significantly impact children's active commuting behavior. They emphasized the need for improving urban design to influence children's commuting choices, with a particular focus on enhancing routes and neighborhood characteristics to encourage active modes of transportation to school.

Lina Kattan, et al. (2011) In a study conducted by Lina Kattan et al. in Calgary, Alberta, the focus was on evaluating the speed limits in the vicinity of schools and playgrounds. The researchers examined 16 playgrounds and 11 schools within the city and measured various parameters related to vehicle speeds, including the 85th percentile speed, mean speed, and speed compliance. To assess the speeds, a reduced speed limit of 30 km/h was implemented near the marked playgrounds and schools, with the aid of traffic signals. The study recorded data during specific peak hours, from 8:00 am to 4:30 pm for schools and from 8:30 am until sunset for playgrounds. Measurements were taken only under dry weather conditions to eliminate the effects of weather. A total of 4,580 vehicle speeds were recorded, and the 85th percentile speed and mean speed were used to analyze changes in traffic speed. The researchers found that the overall mean speed was 32.96 km/h with a standard deviation of 6.61 km/h. The 85th percentile speed was found to be 38.8 km/h. Interestingly, 54.43% of vehicles exceeded the 30 km/h limit, and only 10% of vehicles drove at speeds more than 10 km/h over the speed limit. The results indicated that school zones had a higher rate of compliance but lower mean speeds compared to playground zones. Furthermore, two-lane roads showed better compliance compared to four-lane roads. The presence of fencing, traffic control devices, speed display devices, and the presence of children also influenced speed compliance. The study emphasized the need to enhance the effectiveness of speed limits in school and playground zones based on these findings.

Nasrudin N. et al. (2013) In a study conducted by Nasrudin N. et al. in 2013, the researchers explored the factors influencing the choice of transportation mode for school journeys and also examined the level of awareness among parents regarding the environmental benefits of sustainable vehicles. During peak hours, schools often experience congestion due to the high volume of vehicles. The most commonly observed modes of transportation were school buses and cars, while fewer children walked or cycled to school. The study findings indicated that a significant proportion of parents preferred using private vehicles for transporting their children to school due to convenience and the ability to reach the destination quickly. The use of private vehicles emerged as the most prevalent mode of transportation among the surveyed parents.

Lars B. Christiansen et al. (2014) In a study conducted by Lars B. Christiansen et al. in 2014, the focus was on school transport and the walkability of sites near schools. The researchers selected 1,250 students aged between 11 and 13 years and conducted the study in 14 schools located in

southern Denmark. The main areas of investigation were the distance between students' homes and schools, the school sites in relation to transportation options, and the residential density of the surrounding areas. The study findings indicated that children were willing to cycle distances of up to 4 kilometers to reach their schools. Based on these findings, the researchers recommended conducting further studies that focus on promoting active commuting and creating safe environments for pedestrians. The goal is to develop strategies and interventions that encourage more students to engage in active transportation modes, such as walking and cycling, for their daily school commutes.

Lesley Strawderman, et al. (2015) In a study conducted by Lesley Strawderman et al. in 2015, the researchers investigated driver behavior and accident frequency in school zones. They specifically examined the effect of sign saturation on driver attention. The research was conducted in the state of Mississippi, United States, where they observed driver behavior near school zones and assessed the impact of sign saturation on accident frequency in the surrounding areas of schools. Four schools were selected for the study, taking into account essential elements such as the presence of sign boards, the number of road lanes, sign types, accident frequency, and speed calming measures. Data collection took place over a period of 168 hours, covering a span of seven days and 24 hours. Additionally, the study required the collection of traffic collision data for each school zone over the course of a year. The findings highlighted that the number of signs in a school zone could potentially lead to driver inattention if there is an excessive amount. Factors such as the number of lanes (two-lane or four-lane), the presence of children, the length of the speed zone, and the presence of fencing were found to influence vehicle speeding. Overall, the study shed light on the relationship between driver behavior, sign saturation, and accident frequency in school zones. It emphasized the need for thoughtful consideration of signage placement and other factors that affect driver attention and safety in order to mitigate accidents and promote a safer environment for school zone transportation.

Shailaja Tetali, et al. (2016) In a study conducted by Shailaja Tetali et al. in 2016, the focus was on examining the modes of travel to school among children in urban areas of Hyderabad. The researchers conducted a questionnaire survey targeting children between the ages of 11 and 14 who attended government, private, and semi-private schools. To accurately measure the distance between home and school in Hyderabad, Google Earth was utilized. A total of 48 schools were selected based on socio-economic status for data collection. A questionnaire consisting of 21 questions related to distance, mode of travel, and children's perceptions of road safety was prepared. Out of the 48 selected schools, 45 agreed to participate, resulting in a response rate of 99%. The survey findings revealed that among the participants, 57% of children walked to school, 6% cycled, and 36% used private transport. Private schools had a higher prevalence of motorized vehicle use (41%) compared to government schools (24%). It was also observed that as the distance between home and school increased, there was a higher likelihood of using motorized vehicles. Children residing near their schools were more likely to cycle or walk. Moreover, the study found that fewer girls cycled to school compared to boys. Based on the research findings, it is evident that a significant number of children in Hyderabad prefer to cycle or walk to school. Therefore, it is crucial to prioritize the maintenance of safe and pleasant environments to ensure the well-being and safety of children who choose these active modes of transportation.

Milad Mehdizadeh et al. (2017) In a study conducted by Milad Mehdizadeh et al. in 2017, the focus was on active school travel and the factors influencing the choice of active travel modes to school. The research was conducted in Rasht, Iran, involving data collection from nine schools among children aged 7-9 years. The study findings revealed that several factors played a significant role in influencing active school travel. These factors included household income, accessibility to public transport, attending public schools, and vehicle ownership. The researchers analyzed these factors to understand their impact on the choice of active travel modes, such as

walking or cycling, to school. The purpose of this research was to identify thresholds and gather information to aid in the planning of transportation and roads around schools. By understanding the factors that influence active school travel, policymakers and urban planners can make informed decisions to promote safe and sustainable modes of transportation for school journeys.

Nishant Singh, et al. (2018), In a research study conducted by Nishant Singh et al. in 2018, the focus was on school-based travel mode choice in Kanpur, India. Data were collected from nine schools through a questionnaire survey. The researchers also gathered additional information, including route characteristics and the distance from home to school. The survey findings revealed that younger children were less inclined to bicycle, particularly in the presence of traffic. However, no significant difference in mode choice was observed based on age. Moreover, it was found that girls were less likely to choose bicycling as a mode of travel to school compared to boys. The study also highlighted the influence of family income and the distance from home to school on travel mode choice. These factors played a role in determining whether children opted for active modes of transportation, such as bicycling or walking, or relied on other modes of travel. Overall, the research emphasized the importance of considering various factors, such as age, gender, family income, and distance, when analyzing travel mode choices among school children in Kanpur. By understanding these factors, interventions and policies can be developed to promote safe and sustainable modes of transportation for students.

Khattak et al.(2020) This research investigated various aspects of school zone safety, including the effects of speed differentials on drivers' speeds in active school zones, the effects of school and surrounding characteristics on drivers' speeds in active school zones, and the safety benefits and costs associated with active school zones. For data collection, the research team identified 18 schools in Nebraska and collected drivers' speed data, school and surrounding characteristics, and crash data reported between 2014 and 2018. The 18 schools were categorized based on the speed limit differentials in their school zones, including 35 to 25 mph, 40 to 25 mph, 30 to 25 mph, and 35 to 15 mph. The collected motor vehicle-related data included vehicle classification, vehicle speed, and time of observation. In total, 378,506 vehicles were observed at the study sites. Analysis of the motor vehicle speed data showed that drivers at 17 of the 18 schools significantly reduced their speeds in response to active school zones.

Dias et al.(2021) The focus of this research was to address pedestrian safety issues related to the risky behavior of school children in the Colombo zone. Data collection for the study was conducted across three categories, namely road inventory data collection, road crash data collection, and pedestrian road risk behavior data collection. The study placed particular emphasis on two factors: user behavior at pedestrian crossings and user behavior on sidewalks. Manual data collection was carried out to assess the pedestrian behavior risk, with a specific focus on school uniformed children. Past road crash data from the Sri Lankan Traffic Police database were also utilized to calculate normalized values. By estimating behavior risk values for each school zone, the study aimed to identify the need for any safety improvements. On average, the vulnerability for not using sidewalks was found to be 15%, while the vulnerability for not using pedestrian crossings was less than 10% across all school gates, both in the morning and afternoon times. The results indicated that the vulnerability risk was relatively low compared to findings from existing literature on the subject.

Rusmandani et al.(2022) The objective of this study was to inventory the variables utilized for determining pedestrian crossing facilities. The results obtained indicated that, aside from pedestrian and vehicular traffic, it was essential to consider factors such as road type, pedestrian speed, and passing vehicle speed when making recommendations for crossing facilities.

Kirk et al.(2023) With a focus on reducing the fear of crime among elementary school students, this study explored the relationship between pedestrian volume and fear of crime in elementary

school zones. The results revealed that fear of crime was more prevalent in areas with low and high pedestrian volumes compared to those with average volumes. Interestingly, even in high pedestrian traffic areas where natural surveillance was improved, the primary determinants of heightened fear of crime were human factors, such as the presence of strangers and peers engaged in bullying. These findings have significant implications for architects, building engineers, and urban planners, as they can use them to effectively plan and design schools and public facilities in school zones. Additionally, policy makers can utilize these findings to develop accurate and effective guidelines pertaining to the positioning of patrol personnel or surveillance measures.

5. GLOBAL GUIDELINES

- **World Health Organization & UNICEF (2008)** A research study on child road safety injuries revealed that children between the ages of 5 to 14 are particularly vulnerable and account for 3-15% of injured children. The study also highlighted that boys are nearly twice as likely as girls to be involved in road accidents. In order to reduce traffic accidents and enhance child safety, the researchers proposed several measures. These include the use of protective equipment within vehicles, discouraging drinking while driving, promoting the use of helmets for cyclists and motorcyclists, implementing and enforcing reduced speed limits near schools, and establishing separate lanes for cyclists and sidewalks for pedestrians. By implementing these measures, it is possible to effectively reduce road traffic injuries among children.
- **IRAP**, The International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP), in collaboration with government agencies, research institutes, and NGOs, is actively involved in efforts to improve road safety and create safer environments. As part of their work, they conducted a study focused on enhancing the school environment. The study revealed that collisions between pedestrians and vehicles predominantly occur when pedestrians walk along vehicle routes, during road crossings, when children play on the road, and while boarding or alighting public transport vehicles. To effectively reduce pedestrian traffic collisions, it is crucial to implement infrastructure improvements that address these specific areas of concern. One concept introduced by iRAP is the star rating system, which aims to assess and rate the safety level of road infrastructure. This system helps identify areas where improvements are needed and provides guidance on enhancing the safety features of roads surrounding schools. By utilizing the star rating concept and implementing appropriate infrastructure improvements, iRAP and its collaborating organizations are striving to create safer environments for pedestrians, particularly in school zones, and mitigate the risks associated with pedestrian-vehicle collisions.

6. GOVERNMENT POLICY BASED GUIDELINES (INDIA)

- **NRSP, National Road Safety Policy (2018)** The Indian government introduced a National Road Safety Policy in 2018, which prioritized the safety of vulnerable road users, including children. Recognizing that children's cognitive skills to navigate complex traffic situations are still developing, the policy emphasized the importance of considering their safety. As per the policy, the design and construction of all road spaces and movement areas, whether in rural or urban areas, would be undertaken with a focus on ensuring the safety of children. This implies that infrastructure planning and development would be carried out in a manner that takes into account the specific needs and vulnerabilities of children as road users. By incorporating these measures into road design and construction, the government aims to create safer environments for children, enabling them to navigate road spaces with reduced risks and ensuring their well-being.
- **Road safety audit (IRC SP 88- 2010)** The Indian Road Congress has developed a manual on Road Safety Audit that outlines principles for road design aimed at enhancing the safety of

both road users and pedestrians. One of the key principles highlighted in the manual is the importance of preventing vehicles from parking on sidewalks, as this can adversely impact pedestrian safety. Recognizing pedestrians as a significant group of vulnerable road users, the manual emphasizes the need to prioritize their safety by providing dedicated attention. The manual provides specific guidelines for various aspects of road design, including pedestrian crossings, junctions, road width, curves, road signs, and parking spaces. By following these guidelines, road designers and planners can create safer environments that segregate pedestrians from vehicles, reducing the risks associated with their interaction. This ensures that pedestrian safety is given detailed consideration and that road design promotes the well-being of all road users.

- **Indo-HCM** The Indo-HCM (Indian Highway Capacity Manual) provides guidelines for creating safe pedestrian facilities and environments. According to these guidelines, a minimum space of 0.35m x 0.51m (with a total area of 0.18m²) is required for pedestrians to walk freely on the road without any baggage. If pedestrians are carrying baggage, the recommended space increases to 0.52m x 0.51m (0.26m²). The Indo-HCM also outlines various crossing facilities that enhance pedestrian safety. These include zebra crossings, signalized crossings, pelican crossings, puffin crossings, and toucan crossings. These different types of crossings offer pedestrians designated areas to safely cross the road, minimizing the risk of conflicts with vehicles. In situations where conflicts between vehicles and pedestrians are prevalent, the use of stairways is recommended. These stairways provide an alternative means for pedestrians to cross roads and help reduce potential conflicts. By adhering to the guidelines outlined in the Indo-HCM, road designers and planners can ensure that adequate space is allocated for pedestrians, appropriate crossing facilities are implemented, and measures are taken to minimize conflicts between pedestrians and vehicles. This contributes to the creation of safer pedestrian environments and enhances overall pedestrian safety.
- **IRC 103-2012** The Indian Road Congress has issued "Guidelines for Pedestrian Facilities" that specifically address the improvement of school zones to create safer environments for children traveling to and from school. The guidelines outline several key recommendations for enhancing safety in these areas. Firstly, it is advised that schools should not be located on arterial roads, as these tend to have higher traffic volumes and speeds. Instead, safer routes for walking and cycling should be established to ensure the well-being of children. Furthermore, the guidelines emphasize the importance of wider footpaths near schools to accommodate larger groups of child pedestrians. These footpaths should be kept clear from obstructions, allowing for safe and unimpeded passage. To mitigate congestion and enhance safety, separated drop-off and pick-up areas should be provided in close proximity to the school. This measure helps to minimize conflicts between vehicles and pedestrians, promoting a smoother flow of traffic. By adhering to these guidelines, authorities can effectively improve school zones, creating safer environments for children during their commute to and from school.

7. SUMMARY

This review article focuses on the reassessment and enhancement of pedestrian facilities within school zones with the aim of improving safety. It critically evaluates existing infrastructure, policies, and practices while proposing strategies for redesigning and optimizing pedestrian facilities. The study begins by examining the current state of pedestrian safety in school zones, highlighting the challenges and risks faced by pedestrians, particularly students. Factors contributing to accidents and injuries are explored, including inadequate crosswalks, insufficient signage, and limited visibility. To address these issues, the paper proposes a comprehensive framework for reassessing and enhancing pedestrian facilities in school zones. The framework encompasses multiple aspects, including infrastructure improvements, policy interventions, and

community engagement. Recommendations for infrastructure enhancements include the installation of well-marked crosswalks, speed reduction measures, improved signage, and increased visibility through lighting and reflective materials. Policy interventions suggested include stricter speed limits, traffic regulation enforcement, and regular safety audits. The involvement of the community, including parents, teachers, and local authorities, is emphasized to advocate for safer pedestrian infrastructure and promote awareness and education. Drawing upon existing research studies and successful case examples, the review provides valuable insights and practical recommendations for improving pedestrian facilities in school zones. The goal is to create an environment that prioritizes the safety of pedestrians, particularly school children, and reduces the likelihood of accidents and injuries. By implementing the proposed strategies, the review seeks to enhance overall safety and well-being for all pedestrians in school zones.

REFERENCES

1. Hume C, Timperio A, Salmon J, Carver A, MSc, Billie Giles Corti, PhD, David Crawford, PhD (2009); "Walking and Cycling to School Predictors of Increases Among Children and Adolescents" .
2. Jenna R. Panter, Andrew P. Jones, Esther M.F. Van Sluijs, Simon J. Griffin, DM (2010) "Neighborhood, Route, and School Environments and Children's Active Commuting".
3. Kattan L., Tay R., Acharjee S. (2011) "Managing speed at school and playground zones".
4. Kumar, A., 2023. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal.
5. Nasrudin N., Rahim N., (2013) "Travelling to school: transportation selection by parents and awareness towards sustainable transportation"
6. Christiansen L. B. et al. (2014) "School Site walkability and active school transport-association, mediation and moderation"
7. Strawderman L, et al. (2015) "Driver behavior and accident frequency in school zones: Assessing the Impact of sign saturation", 118-125.
8. Tetali S., et al. (2016) "How do children travel to school in urban India? A cross-sectional study of 5,842 children in Hyderabad."
9. Kumar, Ajay & Yadav, Onkar & Kumar, Sagar. (2023). AN OVERVIEW ARTICLE ON INCORPORATING HUMAN HAIR AS FIBRE REINFORCEMENT IN CONCRETE. 11. 967-975.
10. Mehdizadeh M. et al. (2017) "Walking time to school, children active school travel and their related factors".
11. Kumar, P. and Alam, M.F., Seismic Analysis of RC Building with Steel Bracing.
12. Singh N, Vasudevan V. (2018), "Understanding school trip mode choice-The case of Kanpur India", 283-290.
13. Kumar, A., Yadav, O. and Kumar, A.N., A REVIEW PAPER ON PRODUCTION OF ENVIRONMENT FRIENDLY CONCRETE BY USING SEWAGE WATER.
14. Khattak, Aemal & Kang, Yashu. (2020). Research on School Zone Safety.
15. Dias, Ishani & Wickramarachchi, Dulaj. (2021). Analysing Pedestrian Safety in School Zones Based on Behaviour Risk. Engineer - Journal of the Institution of Engineers, Sri Lanka. 54. 25-35. 10.4038/engineer.v54i4.7468.

16. Rusmandani, Pipit & Jepryadi, Kornelius. (2022). A Brief Review: Variable for Determining the Design of Pedestrian Crossing Facilities. RSF Conference Series: Engineering and Technology. 2. 198-202. 10.31098/cset.v2i2.573.
17. Yadav, O. and Kumar, C., 2023. An Investigation of Ultra High Performance Concrete for the Durability Properties: Literature Survey. *Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science*, 2(8), pp.11-18.
18. Kirk, Boyun & Ha, Mikyoung & Lee, Soyeon. (2023). The Relationship between Children's Fear of Crime and Pedestrian Volume in School Zones. *Journal of Asian Architecture and Building Engineering*. 10.1080/13467581.2023.2172346.
19. Kumar, D., Singh, A., Kumar, P., Jha, R.K., Sahoo, S.K. and Jha, V., 2020. Sobol sensitivity analysis for risk assessment of uranium in groundwater. *Environmental Geochemistry and health*, 42, pp.1789-1801.
20. Kumar, P., Agarwal, S., Bhushan, M., Aind, S.P. and Shyam, G.M., 2022. Groundwater Contaminant Transport Analysis and Numerical Solution of Diffusion in Saturated Aquifer. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SPECIAL EDUCATION*, 37(3).
21. IRC 102-2012 "Guidelines for Pedestrian Facilities". (2012), Indian Roads Congress, New Delhi
22. Indo-HCM "Indian Highway Capacity Manual" (2018), Central Roads Research Institute, New Delhi.
23. Yadav, O., Kumar, A. and Kumar, M., 2023. Literature Survey on Evaluation of High Volume Fly Ash (HVFA) Concrete Mechanical Properties after Being Exposed to High Temperatures. *Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science*, 2(8), pp.19-26.
24. IRAP - Pedestrian Vehicle Crashes. (2016), Road Star rating Guidelines, International Road Assessment Programme.
25. Kumar, A. and Yadav, O., 2023. Concrete Durability Characteristics as a Result of Manufactured Sand. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 4(3), pp.120-127.
26. Kumar, N., Kumar, P., Kumar, A. and Kumar, R., 2023. An Investigation of Asphalt Mixtures Using a Naturally Occurring Fibre. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT*, 2(6), pp.80-87.
27. Kumar, A., Yadav, O. and Shukla, R., 2023. A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW PAPER ON PARTIAL CEMENT SUBSTITUTION IN CEMENT MORTAR WITH WOOD ASH. *Research in Multidisciplinary Subjects*, 1, p.26.
28. National Road Safety Policy" (2018), Ministry of Road Transport and Highway (MORTH), Government of India.
29. Study on rear seat belt usages and child road safety in India (2019), A Report by Safe Life Foundation, New Delhi.
30. World report on child injury prevention. (2008), World Health Organization & UNICEF